

Einstein's Mass-Energy Equivalence is not applicable to Photon Energy

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Abstract: Electromagnetic energy or light energy is concerned with the motion of photons whose velocities are equal to the speed of light because no photon has mass. This paper proves that Einstein mass-energy equivalence is not applicable to light energy or electromagnetic energy.

Keywords: electromagnetic energy, quantum, velocity, speed of light

1. Introduction

A quantum of light that has no mass is known as a photon. Quanta of light or photons of light are the smallest discrete packets of electromagnetic energy. Photon energy is the energy carried by a single photon. The amount of photon energy is directly proportional to the frequency [1] of electromagnetic waves and thus, equivalently, is inversely proportional to the wavelength.

The momentum of photon is different from the relativistic momentum of a moving particle with relativistic mass [2-4]. The relativistic motion is concerned with a moving particle of relativistic mass whose velocity approaches the speed of light, but not equal to the speed of light. The massless photon has the velocity equal to the speed of light.

2. Massless Photon and Relativistic Mass

Relativistic mass of a particle is concerned with the motion of the particle whose velocity approaches the speed of light. The equation of relativistic mass states that

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (1)$$

Where,

- the rest mass of particle is m_0
- the velocity of particle in motion is v
- the speed of light is c

Einstein's equation of a moving particle with relativistic mass states that

$$E = mc^2 \quad (2)$$

Photon is a massless particle and the velocity (v) of massless particle is equal to the speed of light (c).

By substituting $v = c$ in the equation (1), the relativistic mass (m) must become zero or is equal to the mass of photon.

$$m = \frac{m_0}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{c^2}{c^2}}} \Rightarrow m = \frac{m^0}{0} \Rightarrow m = \infty(\text{infinite}), \text{ which denotes that } m \neq 0.$$

Therefore, the equation of Einstein mass-energy equivalence is not applicable to electromagnetic energy or light energy. Quanta of light refer to massless photons of electromagnetic energy.

3. Conclusion

Electromagnetic energy refers to the energy of photons of light. Photon is a massless particle and velocity of massless particle is equal to the speed of light. In this article, it is proved that the equation of Einstein's mass-energy equivalence is not applicable to the light energy or electromagnetic energy.

References

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